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ECOBIOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE WATERS OF THE BIG ARAL

N.S. Sambayev, T.T. Barakbayev,
Ph.D., Master of Science, Research Fellow of the Aral Branch,
LLP «FRPC»,
Kazakhstan, Kyzylorda, Aralsk

Annotation: Large Aral in its modern form is a natural mega-laboratory, demonstrating the adaptive capabilities of the ecosystem in the conditions of steady growth of salts, changing the balance of salts in different layers of water thickness, as well as geological metamorphization of the bottom and coastal zone. The bays of Chernyshev and Tushchybas are of particular interest from an ecological point of view, where, depending on a specific relatively small interval of depth variation, the stratification of water salinity changes.

Keywords: Big Aral, Chernyshev, Tuschybas, salinity, thermocline

Introduction. As a result of a significant drop in the level, the Aral Sea was divided into two reservoirs with independent hydrological, hydrochemical regimes and biotas already at the end of the 20th century. With the aim of preserving the Small Sea, in 1992, the construction of the separation dam was started in the Berg's Strait. The completion of its construction accelerated the regression and degradation of the biota of the Big Aral [1]. The current area of the Big Aral Sea can only be approximately estimated at 1/10 of the area of maximum replenishment in the 60s of the last century. The main water area continues to dry up, reducing the water level annually from 0.6 to 0.9 m. At the beginning of the 21st century, the western and eastern parts of the water area were also divided into separate ones. And already in 2009, the eastern shallower part of the sea turned into a swamp filled with chemogenic mud and silt. Changes in the level regime and morphometric characteristics of the water area are proceeding at an accelerated pace. Peculiar atmospheric conditions form the aridity of the territory, the aridization coefficient is no more than 0.11-0.15. The potential for evaporation is 20-25 times the amount of precipitation. The imbalance in water supply, evaporation and filtration ranges from 22.6 to 65.4 km³ / year.

The purpose of our research is to study the problems of the ecological and biological state of the reservoirs of the Big Aral.

Formulation of the problem. Research is carried out so that the physical, chemical and biological regimes of the reservoirs of the Big Aral, which have lost about 70 % of their volume over the past half century as a result of the combined action of anthropogenic load and global climatic changes, are in the process of radical restructuring taking place in our territory. These processes are relatively poorly studied. As you know, in the lower reaches of the river. Already in the second half of the last century, there was an acute shortage of water, and about 30 years ago, the runoff at its mouth was reduced to almost zero. But at the end of the 80s, on the territory of the former USSR, people's views on the state of the environment began to change greatly, and the dekhans of Syrdariya are more careful about water resources. As a result, already in the early 90s, the water along the river. Syrdariya began to regularly enter the northern part of the Aral Sea [2-4]. Although the volume of this water was approximately 2-4 times less than the value of the natural runoff (14.9 km^3), it was enough to bypass a significant part of the modern "Small Aral" and further discharge into the Big Aral. Currently, the value of the annual runoff at the mouth of the river. Syrdariya ranges from 3.6 to 9.0 km^3 . Water discharge into the Big Aral in full is carried out mainly in the winter period until April. In the rest of the growing seasons, the runoff to the Syrdariya river decreases and the inflow of water, through regulation, is used to maintain the volume of the Small Aral Sea and lake systems. Figure 1 shows the dynamics of water discharge into the Big Aral according to the data of the RSE "Kazvodkhoz" of the Kyzylorda branch.

Figure 1 – Dynamics of water discharge in Big Aral, m^3/s

Research methodology. Hydrological surveys were carried out on a quarterly basis and this information was compared with the indicators of Kazvodkhoz. Hydrological and hydrochemical observations were carried out in the bays of Tushchybas and Chernyshev of the Big Aral. Sampling was carried out from the surface and bottom layers of water according to generally accepted methods [5]. The concentrations of the main ions in water samples have been determined, significant differences in the component composition and density of these once one whole water bodies have been found among themselves, which may indicate a difference in their physical properties and processes occurring in them. The content of oxygen dissolved in water was determined with a Samara-2B analyzer, pH – CONSORT – C932 and a refractometer – ATAGO. Instrumental determination was duplicated by laboratory methods. Determination of the composition and properties of water was carried out in the laboratory by two methods – titrimetric and colorimetric according to existing methods. Determination of the water class by mineralization and the content of the main ions according to O.A.Alekin [6].

Research results. The modern area of the Big Aral Sea reaches no more than 5 thousand km², including bays up to 1,0 thousand km².

According to research data, over the past 2 years, low water levels have been observed in reservoirs, a decrease in the level and volume of water associated with a low water discharge from the Kokaral dam. The runoff of the Syrdariya River to the Small Aral Sea in comparison with 2016 to 2020, on average every year, gradually decreased to 700 million m³. Especially in autumn, there is a water crisis in all bays of the Big Aral. If in June, at the time of sampling in the reservoir of the Western part of the Big Aral (Aktobe region) up to the border of Uzbekistan, salinity reached from 162 to 170 ‰ (ppm), then at the end of September it was recorded 25 ‰ higher, i.e. it reached 195 ‰. A similar situation is also observed in Chernyshev Bay where the salinity value was 210 ‰, higher than in the border part of Uzbekistan.

Tushchybas Bay is a hyperhaline lake on the territory of the former Aral Sea. Located between the Northern and Western Aral. It is the third largest undying lake on the territory of the Aral Sea, formed as a result of a decrease in the level of the Aral Sea from the bay of the same name on its northwestern outskirts.

After the division of the sea into Small (North) and Big (South) gulfs, Tushchybas was the northernmost part of the Big Aral. In the fall of 2004, the Tushchybas bay separated from the Big Aral. A temporary restoration of communication with the Eastern Big Aral occurs during the spring discharge of a large amount of water from the Small Aral.

Before the beginning of the drying up of the Aral Sea, the Tushchybas and Shevchenko bays separated the Karatup peninsula and the Kokaral island, between which there was a narrow Auzy-Kokaral strait with a depth of no more than 2 m. In

2005, the Shevchenko gulf was partially restored with the help of the Kokaral dam, built in the Berg Strait, the depth of which reached 13 meters.

It must be said that the concentration of water salinity in the bays varies in comparison with the spring and autumn periods. If in the spring periods under the influence of the inflow the salinity decreases, then in the autumn periods the salinity increases by an average of 10-15 %.

At the end of June 2019, during the sampling period, the salinity of water in the surface layer (0-1 m) of Tushchebas Bay, measured by evaporation of 1500 ml of water followed by weighing the obtained dry salt sediment on an analytical balance, was 54-58 ‰. In turn, in the Chernyshov Bay, at that time in the rest of the Western Basin, salinity was 140-145 ‰ in the 0-1.2 m layer – the effect of water was observed against the background of seasonal discharge from the Small Aral Sea. For comparison, in October 2019, on the same Tushchybas bay, the total salt concentration in the same water layer was 70-73 ‰, and in Chernyshev 150-168 ‰.

In a comparative aspect with the above indicators during the research period in 2020, a relative decrease in the water inflow of the Syrdaria River was recorded, which led to a further increase in salinity in the studied bays by an average of 15 %. The gradient of change is mainly related to the hydrological state. In high-water and low-water periods, salinity varies by about 10-25 %. According to the classification of O. A. Alekin belongs to brines, according to the ionic composition – to the sodium chloride group of type II (fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Dynamics of indicators of the ion-salt composition of water in the bays A) Tushchybas; B) Chernyshov of the Big Aral

The distribution of salinity retains the regularity of its growth in the direction from south to north. Due to the progressive drying out in the autumn and filling in the spring period of the Tushchybas Bay and the transition of its water area to the "dry" stage, it is filled with chemogenic mud and silt. The spring period

is due to the intensity of evaporation and the peculiarity of the migration of salts with sedimentation in the basin.

According to research data, in the western basin of the Big Aral in the autumn season, a two-layer vertical stratification of waters was observed. According to the data, a maximum salinity is observed in the bottom layer, which can prevent complete mixing of the reservoir in the coming winter season. Nevertheless, there is a long-term tendency towards a reduction in the bottom salinity maximum. In comparison with similar data from previous years, the maximum salinity in the bottom layer is weakly expressed, which may indicate a gradual transition of the reservoir from the meromictic type to the monomictic. The concentration of dissolved oxygen in the bottom layer of the basin remained practically unchanged, which once again suggests that the bottom layer is isolated from the rest. parts of the water column and the anaerobic environment formed here as a result of the decomposition of organic material under conditions of vertical density stratification. It is worth noting the presence of the smell of hydrogen sulfide in water samples from the bottom horizon, as well as in soil samples taken with a bottom grab.

Analyzing the above studies of the ecobiological state of the reservoirs of the Big Aral, we can say that in recent years, the flow of water into the bays has been greatly reduced. Despite the overwhelming influence of vertical density stratification, some water exchange in the bottom layer can be due to the mechanisms of wave oscillations in the thermocline. In addition, according to the data obtained, bottom currents also respond to wind action due, probably, to the action of a barotropic mechanism [7]. If before 2014-2017, about an average of 6,800 million m^3/s was discharged into the Big Aral, then over the past three years the amount of discharge due to a decrease in runoff has decreased to 4300 million m^3/s . Such an adverse impact may affect the overall deterioration of the ecological biological state.

Conclusion. Modern field observations in all parts of the Big Aral are episodic; most of the regime monitoring hydrometeorological points and stations ceased to exist in the first half of the 1990s, therefore, in this work, a database of seasonal observations of the water level was used. The main goal of this work is to study the ecobiological state, the possibility of modeling the dynamics of the water volume of a basin located in arid conditions, using data from indirect measurements of open sources.

As a brief conclusion, we can say that this analysis indicates the extremely important role of the exchange of water and salts between the bays. Currently, the processes of water exchange, in particular its volume and spatial distribution, are the main factor determining the vertical and spatial structure. In turn, this determines the hydrophysical and hydrochemical parameters of the waters, which determine the general state of the ecosystems of each of the residual water bodies.

Thus, the ecological biological state of the reservoirs of the Big Aral is subject to fluctuations in salinity in the water, due to the unstable hydrological regime in recent years. According to monitoring studies and space surveys, the area of the water area of the bays narrows depending on the water balance, and is also characterized by the peculiarity of salt migration and sedimentation. If in the future there is a deficit of water discharge into the Big Aral, then a gradual deterioration of the ecological biological state in general can be expected.

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